

Terpenoids : Part CIX. Application of β -ketosulphoxides. Syntheses of (\pm)-Dihydrocarvone, Isopulegone and *p*-Menthofuran

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Use has been made of β -ketosulphoxide as an important intermediate to achieve a new synthesis of dihydrocarvone, isopulegone and *p*-menthofuran. 4-Methyl-3,3-ethylenedioxy-1-carbethoxy-cyclohexane was treated with methylsulphinyl carbanion to give β -ketosulphoxide which on desulphurisation with aluminium amalgam in aqueous tetrahydrofuran afforded 4-methyl-3,3-ethylenedioxy-1-acetyl-cyclohexane. This ketal ketone when submitted to Wittig reaction with methylenetriphenylphosphorane, followed by deketalisation, gave (\pm)-dihydrocarvone. Starting with 4-methyl-2,2-ethylenedioxy-1-carbethoxy-cyclohexane and following similar reaction sequence, isopulegone was obtained. For achieving the synthesis of *p*-menthofuran, 4-methyl-2,2-ethylenedioxy-1-acetyl-cyclohexane, obtained through the cleavage of β -ketosulphoxide formed by the reaction of 4-methyl-2, 2-ethylenedioxy-1-carbethoxy-cyclohexane, was submitted to Wittig reaction with methoxymethyl-triphenylphosphorane and the product was cyclised with 90 per cent sulphuric acid to get *p*-menthofuran.

A monocyclic monoterpene ketone, dihydrocarvone occurs in nature in the laevo rotatory form¹. On the basis of chemical degradation and spectral data, the formulation (I) has been assigned to dihydrocarvone. Prior to its isolation from Caraway oil², it was reported to be an artefact derived from dihydrocarveol by chromic acid oxidation³ or from carvone through reduction⁴. A number of syntheses of dl-dihydrocarvone have been achieved in our laboratory⁵⁻⁸. Here we

wish to report a new synthesis of dl-dihydrocarvone by making use of β -ketosulphoxide as the important intermediate. The scheme of the reactions employed to accomplish this synthesis is given in chart 1.

4-Methyl-3,3-ethylenedioxy-1-carbethoxy-cyclohexane (II) was prepared according to the method described in the literature⁶. This was treated with methylsulphinyl carbanion to give β -ketosulphoxide (III) in 70 percent yield. I. R. spectrum showed characteristic peaks at 1702 cm^{-1} (carbonyl), 1045 cm^{-1} . (S—O)⁹. The β -ketosulphoxide was treated⁹ with aluminium amalgam in aqueous tetrahydrofuran to have the ketal ketone (IV) in 50 percent yield after chromatography over alumina, followed by fractionation. I. R. spectrum showed characteristic absorption peaks at 1720 cm^{-1} . (Carbonyl) ; 1095 cm^{-1} (Ketal). The ketal ketone (IV) was submitted to Wittig reaction¹⁰ with methylenetriphenylphosphorane to give ketal (V) in 80 percent yield. The I. R. spectrum exhibited no absorption in the carbonyl region, but had characteristic peaks at 3060, 1650 and 888 cm^{-1} . (methylene double bond). Deketalisation¹¹ of the compound (V) with acetone and hydrochloric acid (10%) at room temperature afforded 2-methyl-5-isopropenyl-cyclo-hexanone (I) in 77 percent yield. The identity of this compound was established through the direct comparison of its I. R. absorptiod spectrum with that of earlier synthetic product. It showed peaks at 3070, 2910, 1705, 1645, 1445, 1355, 1260-1240, 1215, 1180, 1140, 1110, 1085, 1050, 965, 888, 830, 750 and 715 cm^{-1} . It was further characterised through the melting point and mixed melting point (undepressed) of its 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone as well as the semi-carbazone derivatives.

CHART 1

Synthesis of dl-isopulegone : Isopulegone, a monocyclic monoterpene ketone, occurs in conjunction with pulegone in penny royal oil¹². Constitution (VI) has

been assigned to isopulegone on the basis of its relationship to pulegone and isopulegol whose structure have already been well established^{1,2}.

Further confirmation of this structure was sought through a synthesis^{1,4}.

The present communication describes another unambiguous synthesis of isopulegone utilising β -keto-sulphoxide (VIII) to provide the desired intermediate ketone (IX), coupled with Wittig reaction with methylene triphenylphosphorane for the production of isopropenyl group. The reaction sequence employed to achieve the synthesis of isopulegone is depicted in the chart 1.

4-Methyl-2,2-ethylenedioxy-1-carbethoxy-cyclohexane (VII), the starting material, was prepared by the procedure of Mukherji et al^{1,5}. In the synthesis of isopulegone, all reactions, except deketalisation, were carried in the same fashion as in the case of dihydro-carvone. The deketalisation of (X) was done with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid in aqueous acetone^{1,4}. I. R. spectrum of the synthetic isopulegone showed absorption peaks at 3060, 2900, 1705, 1640, 1450, 1370, 1240, 1190, 1120, 1070, 1025, 900, 890, 845, and 755 cm^{-1} . It was also characterised through melting point and undepressed mixed melting point of its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

Synthesis of *p*-menthofuran : *p*-Menthofuran occurs in the oil obtained from the flowering heads of piperment plant^{1,6}. Structure (XI) was given to it on the basis of its oxidation to β -methyl adipic acid and on hydrogenation to a compound, identical with (XIa), derived from isopulegone^{1,7}.

Further confirmation for the structure of *p*-menthofuran was deduced from various syntheses reported in literature^{1,8-20}. These syntheses are limited to pulegone or isopulegone as the starting compound. However, here we wish to report a facile and unambiguous synthesis of *p*-menthofuran, starting with 4-methyl-2,2-ethylenedioxy-1-acetyl cyclohexane (IX). The reaction sequence employed in this synthesis is depicted in chart 2.

4-Methyl-2, 2-ethylenedioxy-1-acetyl cyclohexane (IX) was subjected to Wittig reaction with methoxymethylene-triphenylphosphorane⁹ to give the methoxymethylene derivative (XII) in 55 percent yield after careful chromatography over alumina with *n*-hexane as the eluent. It was characterised through I. R. spectrum which showed characteristic peaks at 1670 cm^{-1} (stretching double bond), 1110 cm^{-1} (stretching C—O bond). The methoxymethylene derivative (XII) when stirred with 10 percent sulphuric acid²¹ under nitrogen atmosphere, resulted in the formation of *p*-menthofuran in 40 percent yield after chromatography over alumina with petroleum ether, followed by careful fractionation under vacuum. During this process first the ethylene ketal and the enol ether are hydrolysed to furnish (XIIa) (not isolated) which further cyclises followed by dehydration to form the furan ring²¹.

I. R. spectrum of the compound showed comparable peaks with those reported^{2,2} for natural *p*-menthofuran at 2950, 1690, 1640, 1570, 1450, 1430, 1400, 1360, 1310, 1275, 1230, 1210, 1150, 1120, 1098-1080, 1065, 1033, 985, 945, 925, 895, 865, 790, 760, 740-720 cm^{-1} . U. V. showed $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}} = 223 \text{ m}\mu$ (ϵ , 5760). Lit²⁰. reports $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ethanol}} = 220 \text{ m}\mu$ (ϵ , 5852).

Experimental

Boiling points and melting points are uncorrected. I. R. spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 infracord, using sodium chloride optics (thin liquid film).

4-Methyl-3, 3-ethylenedioxy-1-acetyl-cyclohexane (IV) : Methyl sulphanyl carbanion was prepared from sodium hydride (1.75 g) and dimethylsulphoxide (18ml.). To the above cooled solution was added tetrahydrofuran (18 ml.) and then dropped ketal ester (11, 4.1g.) slowly with efficient stirring and the stirring was continued for one hour at room temperature. The reaction mixture was poured into cold water, acidified at 0° with hydrochloric acid (4.7 ml.) and extracted thoroughly with chloroform. The organic extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. The solvent was removed to have the β -keto-sulphoxide (III, 3.3 g.) in 70% yield as the thick oil and it was used for the next reaction.

To the solution, prepared by dissolving β -keto-sulphoxide (III, 3 g.) in aqueous tetrahydrofuran (10%, 180ml.), was added freshly prepared aluminium amalgam (5.5 g.) in small pieces with efficient stirring. The stirring was continued for 3 hours at 65°. Thereafter, the reaction mixture was filtered and the residual solid washed well with tetrahydrofuran. The combined filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried and the solvent expelled. The residual oil was chromatographed over alumina (60 g.) with pet. ether-benzene (95:5) as the eluent, followed by fractionation under vacuum to give ketal ketone (IV, 1.1g.) in about 50% yield, b.p. 118°-120°/7-8 mm. $\eta_D^{25} = 1.4669$.

4-Methyl-3, 3-ethylenedioxy-1-isopropenyl cyclohexane (V): Methylene phosphorane was prepared from sodium hydride (0.25 g.) in dimethylsulphoxide (4ml.) and methyltriphenylphosphonium iodide (3 g.) in DMSO (8ml.). To the above cooled solution was added ketal ketone (IV, 1 g.) in tetrahydrofuran (5ml.) with stirring and the stirring continued for 2 hours at 60°. Thereafter, the reaction mixture was poured over crushed ice and extracted thoroughly with petroleum ether (40°-60°) and dried. The solvent was expelled and the residue chromatographed over alumina (30 g.) with petroleum ether followed by distillation under vacuum to give methylene ketal (V, 0.80 g.) in 80% yield, b.p. 95°-96°/8-10 mm. $\eta_D^{27} = 1.4678$. Found: C, 73.31; H, 10.37. $C_{12}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 73.43; H, 10.27%.

2-Methyl-5-isopropenyl cyclohexanone (I): To the ketal (V, 2 g.) was added acetone (36ml.) and hydrochloric acid (10%, 12ml.) and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 hr. Thereafter it was diluted with brine solution (100ml.) and the organic material was thoroughly extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and again with brine solution. After drying and solvent removal, the residue was carefully fractionated under vacuum to obtain the ketone (I, 1.2 g.) in 77% yield, b.p. 85°-88°/5.7mm. $\eta_D^{27} = 1.4642$. Found: C, 79.71; H, 10.33. $C_{10}H_{16}O$ requires C, 78.89; H, 10.59%.

2:4-Dinitrophenyl hydrazone prepared by sulphuric acid method was crystallised (twice) from methanol when yellow needles were obtained, m.p. 115°; mixed melting point with an earlier sample was undepressed. Found: N, 16.99; $C_{16}H_{20}N_4O_4$ requires N, 16.86%. Semicarbazone derivative of the ketone after crystallisation (twice) from ethanol melted at 166°-167°. No depression in melting point was observed when mixed melting point was found with the semicarbazone derivative of an earlier synthetic sample. Found: N, 20.49; $C_{11}H_{19}N_3O$ requires N, 20.08%.

4-Methyl-2, 2-ethylenedioxy-1-carbethoxy-cyclohexane (VII): This compound was prepared according to the method adopted by Mukherji *et al*.¹⁶

4-Methyl-2,2-ethylenedioxy 1-acetyl-cyclohexane (IX): Methyl sulphanyl carbanion was prepared from sodium hydride (1.6 g.) and dimethyl sulphoxide (16ml.). To the above cooled solution was added tetrahydrofuran (15ml.) followed by dropwise addition of ketal ester (VII, 5 g.) slowly with efficient stirring and the stirring was continued for one hour at room temperature. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual manner, followed by solvent removal to give β -ketosulphoxide (VII, 5.5 g.) in about 95% yield as a viscous oil.

To the solution, prepared by dissolving β -keto-sulphoxide (VIII, 5.0 g.) in aqueous tetrahydrofuran (10%, 250 ml.) was added freshly prepared aluminium amalgam (5 g.) in small portions with efficient stirring. After addition the mixture was refluxed along with stirring at 65° for 3 hours. Thereafter, it was worked up in the usual manner. After solvent removal, the

residue was chromatographed over alumina with petroleum ether:benzene (95:5) as the eluent, followed by distillation under vacuum to afford ketal ketone (IX, 2.0 g.) in 52% yield, b.p. 115°/4-5 mm. $\eta_D^{27} = 1.4690$. I. R. spectrum showed prominent characteristic peaks at 1715 cm^{-1} (carbonyl), 1060 cm^{-1} (ketal). Found: C, 66.42; H, 9.17. $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 66.64; H, 9.15%.

4-Methyl-2, 2-ethylenedioxy-1-isopropenyl-cyclohexane (X): Methylene phosphorane was prepared from sodium hydride (0.68 g.) in dimethylsulphoxide (7 ml.) and methyltriphenyl phosphonium iodide (5.76 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (5.7 ml.) under nitrogen atmosphere in the usual way. To this was added ketal ketone (IX, 1.4 g.) in tetrahydrofuran (12 ml.) with stirring and the stirring continued for 2 hours at 60°. It was worked up as usual and the solvent was removed. The residue was chromatographed over alumina (20 g.) with petroleum ether as the eluent followed by vacuum distillation to furnish methylene ketal (X, 1 g.) in 83% yield, b.p. 103°/4-5 mm. $\eta_D^{27} = 1.4642$. Characteristic I. R. absorption peaks appeared at 3080, 1640 and 890 cm^{-1} (Methylene), 1065 cm^{-1} (ketal). Found: C, 73.44; H, 10.37. $C_{12}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 73.43; H, 10.27%.

2-Isopropenyl-5-methylcyclohexanone (VI): To the ketal (X, 0.75) was added acetone (15 ml.), *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.22 g.) and water (2.2 ml.) and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 hour. It was worked up in the usual way. After the solvent removal, the residue was fractionated under vacuum to give (VI, 0.32 g.), in 55% yield, b. p. 80°/4-5 mm. $\eta_D^{27} = 1.4633$. Found: C, 79.04; H, 10.66. $C_{10}H_{16}O$ requires C, 78.60; H, 10.40%.

2, 4-Dinitrophenyl hydrazone prepared by sulphuric acid method in cold, was crystallised twice from ethanol as yellow crystals, m.p. 135°. No depression was observed in mixed melting point with an earlier sample of this derivative. Found: N, 17.24; $C_{16}H_{20}O_4N_4$ requires N, 16.80%.

4-Methyl-1-(1'-methoxymethylene ethyl)-2,2-ethylenedioxy-cyclohexane (XII): Methoxymethylene triphenylphosphorane was prepared from sodium hydride (0.4 g.) in dimethylsulphoxide (4 ml.) and methoxymethylene triphenylphosphonium chloride (5.13 g.) in dimethylsulphoxide (8 ml.) under nitrogen atmosphere in the usual way. To the above cooled solution was added ketal ketone (IX, 1.4 g.) in dimethylsulphoxide (5 ml.) with efficient stirring and the stirring was continued at 60° for 12 hr. Thereafter, the reaction mixture was decomposed with ice cold water and worked up as described earlier. After drying and solvent removal, the residue was chromatographed over alumina (30 g.) with n-hexane as the eluent followed by fractionation under vacuum to afford methoxymethylene derivative (XII, 1.0 g.) in 55% yield, b.p. 117°/4-5 mm., $\eta_D^{27} = 1.4719$. I. R. spectrum did not show any absorption in the carbonyl region. Found: C, 69.11; H, 10.09. $C_{13}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 68.99, H, 9.80%.

***p*-Menthofuran (XI):** A mixture of methoxymethylene derivative (XII, 3 g.) and sulphuric acid (90%

7.2 ml.) was stirred under nitrogen atmosphere for 2 hr. Thereafter it was poured into iced water (100 ml.) and thoroughly extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with brine solution, dried and the solvent was expelled. The residue thus left behind was chromatographed carefully over neutral alumina (100 g.) with petroleum ether followed by fractionation under vacuum to afford *p*-menthofuran (XII, 0.8 g.) in 40% yield, b. p. 95-98°/20 mm. $\eta_D^{27} = 1.4729$. Found : C, 80.08 ; H, 9.33. $C_{10}H_{14}O$ requires C, 79.95 ; H, 9.39%.

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